

Research Paper

Renewable heat generation from waste gasification: Infrared thermal imaging and flue gas emissions monitoring of producer gas flame[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the combustion of Producer Gas (PG), composed of 1.90 % CH₄, 18.50 % H₂, 8.85 % CO₂, 22.20 % CO, 7.40 % H₂O, and 41.15 % N₂, obtained from wood packaging waste gasification. Experiments were conducted using a rising co-current stationary fluidized-bed gasifier coupled with a purpose-built combustion test rig. Flame stability and temperature distribution were analysed through thermal imaging in the 7.5–14 μm spectral range, using a pixel-based correlation method. The flame emissivity was calibrated at multiple points using N-type thin-wire thermocouples and adjusted on the Infrared (IR) thermal camera allowing a simplified dynamic analysis of the flame. Results demonstrate that at an ER (Φ) of 0.85, the PG flame remained stable and uniformly distributed within the combustion chamber. However, at a lower Φ of 0.43, the flame exhibited instability, likely due to reduced flame temperatures, which lower reaction rates and weaken the chemical kinetics governing PG combustion. Additionally, high air-flow rates at this condition contributed to flame perturbation, detachment, and quenching. At ultra-lean conditions ($\Phi = 0.43$ and TL ~ 10 kW), significant flame instability and “neck thinning” were observed. Introducing a small amount of methane (up to 5 %) helped stabilize the flame under these conditions, suggesting a potential strategy for maintaining flame stability during ultra-lean PG combustion. Flue gas emissions were monitored for $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$ and varied from 53 ppm CO, 10 % CO₂ and 55 ppm NO_x to 550 ppm CO, 15 % CO₂ and 275 ppm NO_x. Data analysis highlighted the fuel-prompt NO_x production mechanism at lower flame temperatures where thermal NO_x formation is unlikely to occur. The NO_x emissions increased from 200 ppm to 275 ppm as the TL rose from 20 kW to 25 kW but remained nearly constant under increasing lean Φ conditions. This trend revealed the further evidence supporting the predominance of fuel-prompt NO_x formation.

1. Introduction

Several hard-to-abate industrial sectors (e.g., aviation, shipping, steel, and chemicals) require high-temperature heat for various processes where direct electrification is often infeasible. These sectors collectively consume roughly a quarter of world energy and are responsible for emitting a fifth of total CO₂ emissions [1]. Therefore, a combination of innovative approaches is needed to decarbonise and deeply reduce the related pollutant emissions. To support net-zero emission targets, the adoption of biomass-based low-carbon fuels has emerged as a key strategy. In fact, biomass Producer Gas (PG) or syngas when combusted in premixed mode under lean fuel Equivalence Ratio

(ER, Φ) conditions, it offers promising pathways for decarbonized, and high-efficiency heat generation with minimized NO_x emissions [2,3].

The PG generated from air gasifiers is normally composed of CH₄, H₂, CO₂, CO, H₂O, and N₂. Due to its lower calorific value, it becomes necessary to establish flame at turbulent conditions to achieve stable operation at high thermal load and ultra-lean ER conditions. However, in premixed burners directly coupled with biomass gasifiers, flame control is challenging, being susceptible to flame instability, extinction and blow-off at lean flame operating limits [4,5]. Moreover, employing the thermometry measurement on such combustion systems becomes more complex, while providing the accurate measurement is challenging. In the literature, limited studies systematically explore the

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flame stability characteristics under lean ER conditions, as well as strategies of flame stabilization with CO₂ dilution and CH₄ co-firing [6,7]. Precise measurement of reactive scalars, such as flame temperature and combustion species, is crucial for analyzing flames, controlling combustion instability and proposing stable lean-flame solutions. In particular, the experimental flame temperature measurement is essential for gaining insights into the combustion process, refining flame control mechanisms, and developing advanced combustion state diagnostic and monitoring tools [8]. Moreover, experimental flame temperature data also supports development and validating of predictive numerical models.

Over the past few decades, numerous studies have employed various available flame temperature measurement methodologies such as intrusive (probe-based) [9,10,11] and non-intrusive (optical) measurements [12]. While intrusive methods, such as thermocouples, could disturb the fluid medium but they are often used due to their low cost, reliability, and easier application. Notably, thin wire thermocouples are often employed to validate kinetic modelling and facilitate the development of advanced non-intrusive optical techniques [13,14]. On the other hand, non-intrusive methods such as spectroscopy and thermography (thermal imaging), are expensive which enable fast spatial-temporal measurement. In general, spectroscopy is performed by sensing the emission (emission-spectroscopy), absorption (absorption-spectroscopy), as well as scattering (Raman/Raleigh-Scattering) by the flames using detection and absorption sensors. These sensors operate in a specific range of UV, visible and IR bands and should be selected according to the spectral signature of radicals (OH*, CH*) and molecules (CH₂O*, C₂*, CO₂*) [15,16]. Solid soot particles produce a continuous IR radiation spectrum, which decreases with temperature according to Wein's Law. The gas molecules of H₂O and CO₂ generate discontinuous rotation-emission radiation bands at higher temperatures and cause most of the heat transfer in soot-less flames. Typically, at a certain flame temperature, soot particles and gas molecules emit strong thermal radiations underlying the specific bands of whole spectral region of IR (700 nm – 14000 nm) and visible range (400 nm – 700 nm), respectively [17]. Therefore, knowing the magnitude of the radiation intensity or temperature at the underlying spectrum might serve to develop diagnostic and monitoring tools to explore the combustion state [15]. For example, the detection of black body emissions serves both in radiation thermometry and thermography techniques; the former measures the radiance (W/m²-sr) and the latter converts the radiation into a visible image that, once calibrated, allows for measuring the temperature distribution.

Recent years have seen an increase in thermographic studies conducted on open pool fires or traditional fossil fuel flames in high-temperature environments. For example, Sudheer et al. [18] studied open-fired gasoline flames; the authors inferred flame emissivity mathematically from mass burning rate analysis and compared it with experimental emissivity from the thermal camera in the spectral range (7.5 – 14 μm). They observed emissivity variations along the height of the flame at different diameters (0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 1 m) of fire pools, and noticed exponential increments in flame emissivity with the diameter or flame thickness. In recent years, several studies have used IR thermal cameras to study flame radiation characteristics. For example, Raj et al. characterized turbulent diffusion flames of gasoline and diesel pool fires of various diameters theoretically and experimentally with IR cameras by proposing refined methods [19]. The spatial and temporal distributions of emissivity and flame temperature were observed along radial and axial positions. Flame emissivity decreased along the length and showed higher averaged values in the case of gasoline fuel. However, no variation was noticed between the fuels along the central line or core regions. Loboda et al. presented the spectrographic work concerning the black body spectrum [20,21]. Starting from radiation spectra discussions, authors explored the combustion of various vegetation materials, liquid fuels (alcohol, diesel, gasoline), woods and coal, by using an IR camera with two required spectral bands of 2–5 μm and 7–12 μm. It was

concluded that an IR camera of spectral range 2–5 μm was more suitable for studying species-specific band-pass filters, whereas the range 7–12 μm for studying high-temperature objects such as soot particles screened through the flame. Dupuy et al. investigated forestry (pinaster) fuel-based burner flame and reported soot dominant regime by radiations measurement within 7.5–13 μm range [22]. However, the IR cameras required the emissivity of reference flame to plot the accurate flame temperature field. Pastore et al. discussed the spectral emission range of flame products such as soot particles, H₂O, and CO₂ species, and their effects on flame emissivity [17]. They developed a methodology to experimentally determine the emissivity and relate it with the flame thickness (depth). Agueda et al. gave an overview of experimental methods and investigated the flame emissivity of forest fuel beds in the diameter range > 2 m, wherein they proposed the correlation of emissivity with flame thickness and concluded that flames having a thickness larger than 3.2 m would result in emissivity close to the black body (0.9) [17].

Despite advances, few studies have been found regarding flames of alternative fuels like PG under lean conditions. Moreover, there is a lack of studies on the use of a simplified methodological approaches to analyse PG flame operation, as well as on the use of IR thermographic imaging to obtain flame temperature distribution with a correlation to the emissivity levels. PG is a very promising green fuel, derived from waste biomass, that can support the decarbonization of several hard-to-abate sectors where high temperature combustion is required for industrial applications. However, the use of such alternative fuels also needs the development of novel combustor designs, along with effective methods for flame monitoring and emissions measurement. The approach proposed in this work provides a practical and cost-effective solution for controlling and monitoring PG combustion in industrial high-temperature process burners. Notably, it avoids the need for complex and expensive instrumentation. Specifically, the setup utilizes an infrared (IR) thermal camera equipped with a ZnSe filter covering the spectral band of 7.5–14 μm, enabling detailed observation of the PG flame development. A novel approach is adopted to improve the state-of-the-art technique, wherein flame emissivity is determined and directly adjusted in the IR thermal camera after calibration using thin wire thermocouples at multiple points. Emissivity was calibrated by comparing flame temperatures measured by the IR camera and thermocouples in both flame-on and flame-off states. This alignment enabled accurate, non-intrusive measurement of PG flame temperature fields in a custom-designed combustion chamber. Hence, a novel study is conducted to support the direct use of green PG fuels in the combustion application for cleaner and sustainable high-temperature heating processes. The renewable heat potential of the PG flame is assessed through connecting the gasifier with the PG combustion system. Wherein, the combustion process of PG and methane-enriched producer gas (MPG) is investigated, focusing on flame temperature field, flame stability and flue gas emissions at ultra-lean ER range under various Equivalence Ratio (ER, Φ) and Thermal Load (TL) conditions. Analysis of the time-resolved flame temperature fields provided key information on the feasibility and characteristics of PG combustion. The source mechanism of pollutant emissions is investigated, while the quantitative analysis of NO_x emissions indicated exceptionally low emissions under ultra-lean, turbulent PG combustion conditions.

2. . Material and methods

2.1. Experimental test-rig

2.1.1. Premixed burner

The premixed burner consists of three components: the burner head, the Venturi mixer and the pilot burner. The burner head is where PG-primary air combustion occurs. The burner wall is 4 mm thick which extends 60 mm into the combustion chamber. The Venturi mixer allows for efficient air-fuel mixing, where controlled airflow draws in PG due to

Fig. 1. Premixed flame burner.

the depression induced by a section constriction in the pipe. The small pilot burner, positioned adjacent to the main burner, helps initiate the combustion of the PG-air mixture. Additionally, an optional methane inlet is provided as a y-shape after the mixer as shown in Fig. 1, which works as a backup fuel source for methane co-firing studies and flame stabilization. More details are available in the work of Caligiuri et al. [23].

2.1.2. Combustion chamber design

An optically accessible combustion test rig was designed and constructed to perform fundamental measurements of PG combustion. Several critical factors were considered during the design phase of the combustion chamber, including fuel flexibility, efficient air–fuel mixing, optical accessibility, and a wide range of operational capabilities. The combustion chamber made of stainless steel measures 820 mm × 520 mm × 520 mm, with a burner of 68 mm diameter and 30-kW thermal power capacity. As mentioned before, the burner wall extends 60 mm

into the combustion chamber. A 40 mm thick vermiculite insulation layer was applied to the chamber walls to prevent overheating. Two optical windows are incorporated for non-intrusive measurements: an 80 mm diameter thermal ZnSe window allows for optical-based IR thermal imaging of the producer gas flame, while a 300 mm × 200 mm quartz window permits the analysis of flame shape and flow field. These optical windows allow a specific band of interest from electromagnetic radiations and prevent atmospheric attenuation, for example, the ‘ZnSe window’ is transparent to IR radiations while the thermal shock-resistant ‘Quartz window’ is compatible with the Visible range. In addition to these non-intrusive methods, intrusive measurements are also utilized, including monitoring air–fuel flows, pressure sensors, and Type N thermocouples, which provide temperature data for calibrating the emissivity of flame in thermal camera recordings. Furthermore, a tertiary air inlet is located near the chamber outlet to promote flame dilution and cool the exhaust gases before discharge into the atmosphere. The combustion chamber along with the experimental test rig is shown in Fig. 2.

2.1.3. Gasifier coupling and operation

A commercial biomass gasifier of 40 kg/h capacity and thermal power of nearly 160 kW, provided by Burkhardt GmbH and based on a rising co-current stationary fluidized bed configuration, was operated with woody waste biomass (pellets from disused wood pallets) for PG production. In the schematic of Fig. 2, the coupling of the gasifier with the combustion test rig is presented. Part of the PG flow was extracted via a pipeline directly coupled with the premixed combustion test rig through the Venturi mixer; the rest was bypassed to a flare before leaving to the atmosphere. The air gasifier was operated at a standard inlet temperature and atmospheric pressure conditions. Before the gasifier startup, the availability of a sufficient quantity of wood pellets and the proper functioning of the gasifier components were ensured to facilitate smooth biomass gasification operations. During the experimental campaign, the gasifier attained steady state conditions and provided stable gas composition profiles within 40–60 min once the reactor fluidized bed was ignited.

Fig. 2. Experimental-rig.

Table 1
PG and MPG mixture compositions.

Gas mixture(s)	Methane flow rate [m ³ /h]	CH ₄ [% vol.]	H ₂ [% vol.]	CO ₂ [% vol.]	CO [% vol.]	H ₂ O [% vol.]	N ₂ [% vol.]	LHV [MJ/m ³]
PG	0.0	1.90	18.50	8.85	22.20	7.40	41.15	5.48
MPG1	0.11	3.70	18.16	8.69	21.79	7.26	40.40	6.04
MPG2	0.22	4.64	17.98	8.60	21.58	7.19	40.00	6.33

Fig. 3. Measurements applied to air line of combustion test rig.

Table 2
Measuring equipment for the experimental rig.

Measured property	Measuring principle	Equipment	Accuracy
Air mass flow	Hot wire anemometer	E + E Elektronik EE741	±3% reading, ±0.3 % full scale
Producer gas flow	Thermal mass flowmeter	FCI ST80	±1% reading, ±0.5% full scale
Methane flow	Mass flow controller	Brooks-0254	±1% reading
Flame temperature	N-Type thermocouple	TERSID	±0.25 % reading
In-chamber pressure	IR Thermal Camera	FLIR T1030sc	±2% reading
Flue Gas composition	Capacitive pressure transducer	Keller 41X	±0.1 % reading
	Electrochemical cells gas analyzer	MRU Vario Plus	±10 ppm (CO), ±5 ppm (NO _x)

2.1.4. Producer gas mixtures

PG composition mainly depends on the types of biomass, and oxidizer stream fed to the gasifier, as well as on the operating temperature and pressure of the gasifier. Herein, the PG was obtained directly from the gasification of pellets made of wood packaging waste pallets. The gas properties such as the lower heating value (LHV) of 5.48 MJ/m³, and density at standard thermodynamic parameters (300 K, 1 bar) were calculated using Cantera solver [24] for calculating the thermal loads. Also, adiabatic flame temperature, flame speed, heat release rate and species production profiles were numerically studied at wide-range equivalence ratios $0.4 \leq \Phi \leq 2.4$ in a previous work by Qureshi et al. [25]. PG composition and two blended mixture compositions of methane and PG were used to examine flame stabilization through flame topological studies (see PG and MPG compositions in Table 1). As reported, the modified MPG1 mixture is composed of PG with a small increase in methane up to ~ 4.64 %. The gas properties of the MPG1 mixture were re-calculated to obtain different thermal loads while chemical equilibrium condition was applied to extract modified flame

parameters over a wide range of equivalence ratios. This additional study was conducted at a lower heating load of 9–10 kW and very-lean ER condition, $\Phi = 0.4$ of PG flame. The effects of methane addition and the respective increase of methane flow from 0.11 and 0.22 m³/h (corresponding to 1 kW and 2 kW, respectively) were observed.

2.2. Overview of flow measurements

2.2.1. Air and fuel rate measurements

The PG was spilt out naturally from the gate valve towards the combustion test rig. The measurement of the PG consumption rate was performed using a thermal mass flow meter, installed at the spilt line of the gasifier while the volumetric flow rate signal was acquired using cDaq NI-9203 and the Labview program. The gas mass flow meter is designed for industrial-scale applications, it is accompanied by an advanced 'wet gas' shielding mechanism that could tackle the challenges of measuring gas flows with moist gas or condensation droplets. Additionally, a 99.9 % pure methane cylinder was made available to supply methane for the pilot flame, and to the main burner for combustion studies of blended PG mixtures. To control methane flow rates for the pilot flame and main burner, two independent Brooks mass flow controllers were used with a control unit. That type of controller was adopted due to the possibility of blending multiple streams of gases with quick-generation of flow set-points by micro-computer. As for the air supply unit, as shown in Fig. 3, the radial-type side channel blower SC-401, was used for the supply and control of air streams. The air consumption rate was measured by an anemometer velocity sensor. The anemometer (transmitter) works on the principle of hot film technology and has the capability of sensing very low volumetric flow rates based on a cross-section of pipe with an appropriate correction factor. See Table 2 for instrument details.

2.2.2. Burner operating loads

To this end, a part of the PG flow was bled towards the burner inlet

Table 3
List of producer gas flows, air Reynolds number and burner operating loads.

Mixture (s)	Re_{air} [-]	Producer gas flows [m^3/h]	Methane flows [m^3/h]	Thermal loads [kW]
<i>Producer gas (PG)</i>				
PG	18×10^3	19.84	0	28.09
PG	15×10^3	16.76	0	23.53
PG	9×10^3	10.23	0	14.50
PG	6×10^3	6.94	0	9.80
<i>Methane-enriched producer gas (MPG)</i>				
MPG1	6×10^3	7.43	0.11	11.49
MPG2	6×10^3	5.94	0.22	10.40

Table 4
Measured flue gas emissions data at wide range equivalence ratios and thermal loads.

ER [-]	Thermal loads [kW]	O ₂ [%]	CO ₂ [%]	CO [ppm]	NO _x [ppm]
0.45 – 0.70	10–25	4.19–9.44	10–15	53–550	55–275

with a volumetric flow rate in the range of 6–20 m^3/h . Therefore, the combustion test rig was operated accordingly with TLs up to 30 kW, and wide-range burner operating loads were established during the experimental campaign for a comprehensive combustion study. To operate the burner in stable mode, the required air flows were produced in the turbulent flow regime in the Reynolds number range, $Re_{air} \sim 6\text{--}18 \times 10^3$ at stoichiometric flame conditions. Nevertheless, an additional methane fuel inlet was provided for studying the methane co-fired PG flames for stabilization of highly turbulent very lean flame having $Re \gg 20 \times 10^3$. The nomenclature used for PG mixtures and the detail of the considered flow rate along with corresponding burner loads are given in Table 3.

2.3. Flue gas measurements

A portable electrochemical cell-based flue gas analyzer, MRU (VARIO plus) was used to measure the flue gas emissions of O₂, CO, CO₂, and NO_x (NO and NO₂) during the PG combustion process. The standard operating procedure was implemented during the experimental campaign regarding the setting up of the analyzer, probe insertion, shutting down as well as flue gas emission data collection using an SD card. The calibration of the analyzer and purging of the apparatus was ensured. The saturation of emissions in the combustion chamber was also ensured by considering the sufficient waiting time before accounting for the emissions. In this work, 21 stable operating points were collected in a wide range of TLs and lean ERs and data was post-processed for analysis. To observe the effect of more than one

Fig. 4. Position of thermocouples and optical windows in xyz- coordinate system.

Table 5
Intrusively measured flame temperature at nominal power load 26–28 kW.

ER [-]	T ₂ [°C]	T ₃ [°C]	T ₄ [°C]	T ₅ [°C]	T ₆ [°C]
0.20	829	907	791	662	644
0.60	854	966	877	736	696
0.65	911	1022	919	797	751

parameter on emissions, a response surface method (RSM) was adopted and discussed in the following section.

2.3.1. Data analysis

The flue gas measurements were processed by the RSM analysis using the two independent input variables, ER [-] and TL [kW], against the outputs, such as the O₂ concentration and flue gas emissions CO, CO₂, and NO_x. The RSM is a mathematical technique used to fit polynomial equations to the experimental data which describes the overall behavior of the system. The best operating point can be explored by deepening the data correlations between several input variables against multiple outputs. For this study, the ‘21’ operating points were firstly selected from the merged data frame of LabView and MRU files in variable ranges $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$ and $10 \text{ kW} \leq \text{TL} \leq 25 \text{ kW}$. The data points were included in the RSM model developed for analysis using a Python code environment. It can be seen in Table 4, that the regression model was built on a wide range of experimental data sets to make the correlation between inputs (ER and TL) and output variables (O₂, CO, CO₂, and NO_x). The residuals were also monitored during RSM analysis to observe the percentage difference between the RSM model and the experimental data. Initially, the numerical regression results were not found reliable because of poor polynomial curve fitting i.e., $R^2 = 0.36$, in the case of CO₂ and NO_x emissions. Before the final analysis, air and PG flow rate data was cleaned and smoothed using statistical methods. Data reliability was ensured by keeping the standard deviation (SD) values much lower, i.e., $\text{SD} \sim 4.0$, after the outliers (below 5 % and above 95 % of the average

flow rate) were removed until the fitting above $R^2 = 0.80$ was achieved for CO₂ and NO_x emissions. Similarly, $R^2 = 0.95$ and $R^2 = 0.97$ values were used to present the O₂ concentrations and CO emissions.

2.4. Applied thermometry measurements

2.4.1. Intrusive temperature measurement

As shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b), sketches of the combustion chamber are given considering the xyz-coordinate system to understand the reference thermocouple locations inside the combustion chamber and 2D flame projections at the yz-plane. The intrusive flame temperature measurements at a nominal TL of 26–28 kW were taken at specific locations of the combustion chamber in the flame zone, wherein flame exists, and post-flame zone to measure the flue gas temperature near the chamber outlet. To this aim, four thermocouples such as T₁, T₂, T₃, and T₄ were installed in the reaction zone at different heights above the burner that were placed in parallel with each other however at different depths from the axis of symmetry to cover the flame core and flame side regions. For example, the thermocouples (TC) T₁ and T₃ cover the flame core region, which was placed at heights $Y_1 = 40 \text{ mm}$, $Y_3 = 140 \text{ mm}$, and at distance $Z_1 = Z_3 = 0$ from the symmetrical axis, whereas T₂ and T₄ cover the side regions of the flame and were placed at heights $Y_2 = 90 \text{ mm}$, $Y_4 = 190 \text{ mm}$ and at distance $Z_2 = Z_4 = 35 \text{ mm}$. For this purpose, fine thin wire N-type thermocouples were used and the flame temperature data was acquired using the cDAQ NI-9213. Moreover, T₅ and T₆ were placed near the chamber outlet to measure the post-flame zone and were placed at heights $Y_5 = 500 \text{ mm}$, $Y_6 = 550 \text{ mm}$ and at distance $Z_2 = Z_4 = 0 \text{ mm}$.

The temperature coordinates are T₁ (40, 0), T₂ (90, 35), T₃ (140, 0), T₄ (190, 35), T₅ (500, 0), and T₆ (550, 0) and measured data is given in Table 5. The thermocouple at coordinate T₁ (40, 0) was probed very close to the pilot flame, therefore, it was not included in the analysis to avoid the pilot flame effect on interpreting results of a main burner

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of infrared thermal imaging technique used in this work.

Fig. 6. The raw thermal images of flames captured using IR thermal camera of 30 Hz frequency in the emission spectrum 7.5–14 μm .

Fig. 7. Inserted thermocouple probes into the PG flame confined in the combustion chamber for emissivity calibration in the IR thermal camera.

flame. Moreover, the thermocouple at coordinates T_5 (500, 0), and T_6 (550, 0) are located high above and can not be seen in the flame projections taken through optical windows.

2.4.2. Infrared thermal imaging

The configuration of the non-intrusive thermometry is illustrated by a schematic diagram in Fig. 5. In general, the target (flame) acts as the

thermal radiation source to be measured. A lens confines the field of view, while a bandpass filter determines the portion of the spectral region in the electromagnetic spectrum to be measured. The detector serves as the sensor that detects the heat energy or photons. In principle, the collected energy causes the detector to generate the voltage, which is then converted into a digital count. Detectors can be of several types ranging from thermal detectors (made of metal or semiconductor materials) to quantum detectors (made of InSb, InGaAs, PtSi, HgCdTe). Nevertheless, the implementation of radiation thermometry is challenging because the thermal camera lens receives the radiation from the object and the environment. Therefore, to solve the atmospheric attenuation issue, a bandpass filter should be selected with the required wavelength range, and a sensor with the required sensitivity. To accurately determine the target temperature, knowledge about target emissivity, temperature of the environment and proper camera specifications are required. However, the emissivity factor is uncertain and thus a correction method is needed. Moreover, to capture a good image, a proper Field of View (FOV) needs to be defined, which determines the total surface area that varies along with the distance and focal plane. IR Thermal Camera FLIR – A700 of the spectral range 7.5–14 μm was employed in the confined PG flame with 30 Hz acquisition frequency. Intrusive measurement of flame temperature was performed using thin wire N-type thermocouples. Among the main components of this imaging technique, the ZnSe thermal window (bandpass filter) was located on the chamber along the yz-face and the IR camera (lens) was placed close to the window facing the yz-plane, therefore flame was projected as a 2D image.

As shown in Fig. 6, flame thermal images are captured with a thermal camera during PG combustion. These flame images do not represent the

Fig. 8. The real-time biomass-derived PG composition profiles.

PG flame temperature; instead, these images are based on the radiometric RGB scale, which also includes background noise, due to which it is hard to identify the flame zones. Therefore, the flame images are processed through algorithms developed for the removal of background noise, intensifying the flame zone and rescaling of flame images for flame temperature correction. The detailed description of image processing methods applied to raw flame images is available in Appendix A.

2.5. Emissivity correction

Since the direct assessment of the emissivity range is uncertain, it affects the accuracy of the flame temperature evaluation. In this work, the emissivity is determined from an IR thermal camera wherein the emissivity factor was adjusted after calibration via probing thin wire N-type thermocouples into the PG flame as a priori for emissivity correction as shown in Fig. 7. The thermometry work was performed with 'ZnSe' glass window mounted on the combustion chamber, which filters the long-wave IR radiations with spectra in 7.5–14 μm band. The emission spectrum of H_2O and CO_2 molecules is treated as uniform; thereby, emissivity is taken as an averaged value to simplify the calibration process. The radiation heat loss from thin-type thermocouples is neglected due to the relatively much thicker PG flame compared to the diameters of thermocouples, whereas the flame reflectivity is considered zero, assuming that the surrounding surfaces are non-reflective, as chamber walls are made of a refractory material painted with a high-temperature black painting. During the preliminary tests, the background temperature was measured to improve the accuracy of the thermal camera read since the flame has a low emissivity and the readings of the thermal camera can be affected by the surrounding objects; this was done by running the combustion at nominal load for 30 min till the steady-state condition was reached; then the combustion chamber wall temperature was measured with a thermocouple in flame-OFF conditions to set the background noise. Later, thermal camera

videos were recorded at various TLs and ERs points with and without thermocouples. During the measurements, the average emissivity value was adjusted according to acquired temperature value by the thermocouple at specific TLs and ERs points. For instance, the emissivity factor, $\varepsilon \sim 0.2$ was selected to calibrate a non-intrusive flame temperature field correlated with intrusive thermocouple temperature of 1022 $^\circ\text{C}$ at nominal TL and slightly lean flame conditions. Moreover, flame images were exported at chosen operating options to be processed at subsequent stages of data analysis.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the results related to different aspects of PG flame at varying TL and ER (Φ) are discussed in detail to evaluate the renewable heat generation potential of green PG fuel. The PG flame was established in a combustion test rig supplied with residual green PG directly sourced from the gasifier. Despite the challenges involved in the flame tests, they provided novel insights into combustion thermometry and flue gas emissions, which might help in advancing the development of sustainable heat production technologies. The main findings include PG flame stability, flame temperature, and pollutant emissions. The flame stability characteristics are presented after implementing flame image processing techniques on the raw IR flame images to intensify the flame zone. Moreover, a novel flame temperature measurement methodology was developed for these complex flame tests and provided reliable results related to time-resolved and average flame temperature distribution.

3.1. PG composition

The real-time profile of PG compositions and reactor temperatures during the experimental campaign evidenced stable wood packaging waste gasification. It was observed that once the ignition of wood pellets

Fig. 9. Intrusive flame temperature profiles (T_2 , T_3 , T_4 , T_5 and T_6) above the burner at a nominal TL.

Table 6

Percentage difference of PG flame temperature measured with TC and IR imaging at ER, $\Phi \sim 0.85$.

Flame Temperature [°C]		Position [mm] (y, z)	Difference [%]
TC	IR		
$T_2 \sim 911$	819	(90, 35)	≈ 11
$T_3 \sim 1022$	943	(140, 0)	≈ 8
$T_4 \sim 919$	939	(190, 35)	≈ 2

happened successfully, the gasifier took almost one hour to reach stable PG composition profiles, as shown in Fig. 8. The steady-state condition was reached as soon as the reactor core gasification temperature peaked at 800 °C. The gasifier provided constant PG composition and stable flow rate, part of which was fed to the burner inlet with the help of a venturi mixer at volumetric flow rates up to 20 m³/h. However, during the experimental campaign, small fluctuations in the flow rates of output gas were also observed.

3.2. PG flame temperature, visualization and analysis

Temporally evolving (frame-by-frame) and time-averaged thermal images suggested interesting insights into PG and MPG flames at changing ER and TL conditions. Specifically, the thermal images of

flames provided the flame temperature at different rates and locations inside the combustion chamber. This flame temperature field was precisely correlated with intrusive flame temperature measurement in terms of the magnitude and temperature gradient.

As displayed in Fig. 9, overall the flame temperature decreases downstream towards the outlet of the chamber. More specifically, PG combustion occurred quite effectively in the designed combustion space even at very lean ER ($\Phi \sim 0.20$, 0.60, and 0.65) and high TL (~ 28 kW). Temperature distribution extracted from thermocouples T_2 , T_3 , T_4 , T_5 and T_6 showed low-temperature gradients along the y-axis that could be associated with an efficient and stabilized PG flame. It was observed quantitatively that the most intense flame zone with the highest flame temperature, T_3 of 1022 °C, was located in the flame core region at $Y_3 = 140$ mm with $\Phi = 0.65$. Moreover, the emissivity correction revealed that, the emissivity value, $\epsilon \approx 0.20$ was found sufficient for the satisfactory correlation between the non-intrusive flame temperature field and intrusively measured thermocouple temperature of 1022 °C. For example, as given in Table 6, percentage difference between PG flame temperature measurement with TC and IR imaging was not exceeded by more than 11 %. This small difference may be due to the absorption of radiation by the atmospheric medium between the flame and the IR camera, which caused a reduction in the flame temperature reading. Overall, the adjusted emissivity factor is in good agreement with the emissivity study of various fuels and flame thickness <0.1 m [26]. Generally, with increasing emissivity factors, the radiation heat transfer towards the surroundings becomes higher. Furthermore, it was noted during the calibration that emissivity significantly altered the flame intensity and thermal distributions due to its strong dependence on radiation heat transfer, although the flame topology remained unchanged.

3.2.1. PG flame shapes and edge graphs

In recent years, research in the field of edge detection methods has been conducted by researchers for clear visualization of open flames or forest fire detection with subsequent warning alarms as well as abnormal flame conditions [27]. However, no relevant studies were applied to confined flames of industrial burners for detecting actual FLIR infrared flame shapes, which is a more challenging task and requires highly contrasting grey-scale image construction and other advanced tools or techniques [28]. In this study, Sobel and Canny edge detection algorithms provided the support for identifying the burner flame shapes; however, the black mask approach was also employed to remove the intense background noise; additional details of this technique are reported in Appendix A. The shape topology of varying flame shapes is

Fig. 10. Flame edge graphs at different time rates and ER conditions.

Fig. 11. Time-resolved thermal images of PG flames at different time rates for $\Phi = 0.85$.

Fig. 12. Fluctuations of PG flame temperature measured using thermal camera at 30 Hz at the yz-flame coordinate (106,0). $\Phi = 0.85$ (orange color); $\Phi = 0.43$ (blue color).

Fig. 13. Time-resolved thermal images of PG flame at different time rates and ER, $\Phi = 0.43$.

shown in Fig. 10. The top rows of flame edge graphs suggested quasi-stable flame conditions at $\Phi = 0.85$; however, the bottom rows predicted the abnormal or unstable behavior of the PG flame at lower ER, $\Phi = 0.43$.

3.2.2. Time-resolved PG flame images

Flame shape topology and temperature field analysis provided a deep understanding of the PG combustion behavior, and combustion state and forecasted the onset of flame instability events. For the PG flame comparison, different TL and ER conditions were considered. This analysis aimed to explore the flame control mechanisms, particularly during flame stabilization and instability events. The variation in TLs influences turbulent premixed flames due to several competing factors, such as turbulence intensity, thermodynamic parameters, fuel-air mixture strength, and the burner geometrical configuration. However, this section focuses on the influence of ERs. As shown in Fig. 11, the time-resolved flame images of the PG mixture were viewed at $\Phi = 0.85$ for flame topology analysis at different frame time 0.066 s, 0.099 s, 0.132 s and 0.165 s. A similar location of a higher-temperature combustion region ($T_f \sim 1000^\circ\text{C}$) was examined at the flame region $130 \text{ mm} \leq Y \leq 212 \text{ mm}$. Hence, the plotted flame temperature contour and measured thermocouple temperature showed satisfactory agreement. These thermographic images do not depict the exact reaction zone, although they identify the transition of burned to unburned regions, as well as the locations of higher temperature zones. At this ER ($\Phi = 0.85$) condition, the PG flame was quite stable and evenly distributed in a

cylindrical flame shape. Moreover, the instantaneous flame images showed analogous flame shapes at temporally evolving time rates, which proved a stable combustion behavior. More interestingly, the flame temperature distribution of the premixed PG flame was slightly different in evolving or frame-by-frame flame images, revealing spatiotemporal variations of the reaction mechanisms inside the combustion chamber.

Moreover, the temporal fluctuations of maximum flame temperature are captured at the central coordinate (y, z) within the flame zone and presented here to give further evidence of the different flame instabilities at varying ER conditions. For instance, Fig. 12 presents further evidence of a quasi-stable flame with a smaller flame temperature fluctuation at an ER ($\Phi = 0.85$) as compared to fluctuations of flame temperature at an ER ($\Phi = 0.43$). This is real time dispersion of flame temperature around the average value which is obtained by the post-processing of nearly six hundred frames using FLIR software and demonstrates the validity of methodology to differentiate the flame instabilities behavior of PG flames. The fluctuating behavior is partly due to flickering flame caused by instabilities that occurred as a consequence of minimal variations of the gas composition and discontinuous IR radiation emissions of gas molecules. Hence, the fluid-dynamic instability may be the main source of flame temporal fluctuations.

Furthermore, when considering the same PG composition, but lower ER condition, different results were obtained. For instance, at $\Phi = 0.43$, the PG flame shapes at consecutive frames were very distinct as shown in Fig. 13 due to several competing factors, related to fluid dynamics and

Fig. 14. Time-resolved thermal images of MPG1 flame at different time rates and ER, $\Phi = 0.40$.

chemical kinetics. Importantly, a decrement in flame temperature ($T_f \sim 800^\circ\text{C}$) was noticed at $\Phi = 0.43$, which may cause the reactions to be slower and may weaken the role of chemical kinetics associated with the PG combustion process. In addition, increased air Reynolds number $Re \gg 20 \times 10^3$ associated with the very low ER contributed to the disruption of vortical structures of turbulent flow, which, in turn, disturbed the flame by generating multiple branches along the flame surfaces. This process led to a fragmentation of the premixed flame surface, altering its topology, flame detachment and quenching due to highly turbulent flow conditions as observed in [29]. Furthermore, flame neck thinning was observed, indicating potential flame stability concerns. Specifically, the flame surface area near the flame neck decreased significantly compared to the surface area further downstream in the combustion chamber. In terms of temperature distribution, a lower flame temperature was detected near the flame neck, close to the burner, primarily due to heat losses to the burner walls.

In terms of the spatial location of higher-temperature regions of flame, it was observed that violent chemical reactions occurred along the symmetrical axis between flame region $130 \text{ mm} \leq Y \leq 212 \text{ mm}$.

This flame imaging study has demonstrated the flame temperature field, flame dynamics, and occurrence of flame de-stabilization events near flame blow-off conditions.

3.2.3. MPG flame images

Flame visualization and flame stability analysis at ultra-lean ER conditions were further analyzed using an MPG mixture. As a result, significant insights were gained regarding the effects of the modified PG mixtures on flame stability characteristics, with a particular focus on the MPG1 mixture. As illustrated in Fig. 14, time-resolved flame images of the MPG1 mixture were viewed at $\Phi = 0.4$ for topology analysis at different frame rates of 0.198 s, 0.231 s, 0.264 s and 0.294 s. The introduction of a small percentage of methane under ultra-lean conditions led to a notable re-stabilization of the flame. Specifically, the flame front shifted backwards toward the burner exit region, and the flame neck thinning phenomenon disappeared. The combustion kinetics were immediately influenced, with more pronounced effects observed as the methane content increased. This enhanced flame stability can be attributed to the slight increase in the calorific value of the MPG1, which

Fig. 15. Time-averaged thermal image of PG flames at ER, $\Phi = 0.85$.

Fig. 16. Time-averaged thermal image of PG flames at ER, $\Phi = 0.43$.

likely resulted in a slightly higher heat release rate near the burner region evidenced by flame temperature ($T_f \sim 800^\circ\text{C}$). Moreover, the restabilization of the flame was linked to improvements in flame front anchoring, with the flame achieving better attachment to the burner region. The increased share of methane improved the reaction rates, as

methane has a higher heat release which contributes to more rapid oxidation reactions compared to the other components of PG. This shift in combustion behavior can be understood through more favorable flame kinetics and reduced strain rates required to sustain stable combustion. Additionally, methane enrichment enhances the flame

Fig. 17. Flue gas emissions O₂, CO, CO₂ and NO_x at varying ER conditions and a wide range of thermal loads (10–25 kW).

propagation speed at lean ER, thus stabilizing the flame at ultra-lean equivalence ratios by compensating for lower reactivity in the other fuel constituents. Furthermore, the heat release distribution across the flame became more uniform, mitigating localized heat losses and improving overall flame symmetry. This even flame distribution reduces the risks of local quenching, enhancing the stability margin and improving the efficiency of the combustion process. The reduction in flame neck thinning also signifies a lower likelihood of instability phenomena such as blow-off, since the flame maintains a more continuous and robust reaction zone.

3.2.4. Time-averaged flames

Thermographic flame visualizations were also performed by time-averaging six hundred instantaneous flame images to analyze the averaged PG flame characteristics. These time frames were found to be optimal for capturing averaged characteristics while minimizing computational cost. While time-averaging can simplify the flame structure, potentially leading to an averaged temperature and flow field, this approach remains crucial for both the combustion device design by predicting the overall flame spread and the validation of Reynolds-Averaged simulations of the combustion process. For example, one of

the most critical design parameters in a combustion chamber is its volume, which can be determined by examining the overall flame size or the region occupied by the burned gases during combustion. Time-averaged flame images were thus processed at different ERs, specifically $\Phi = 0.85$ and $\Phi = 0.43$. This analysis aimed to observe the impact of varying ERs on flame shape and temperature distribution as shown in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16.

The quantitative and qualitative effect of ER on the averaged flame temperature field is the same as observed during time-resolved flame image analysis. For instance, a lower flame temperature was observed at decreased ER, $\Phi = 0.43$. Additionally, the location of higher temperature zones remained the same between the regions, i.e., $130 \text{ mm} \leq Y \leq 212 \text{ mm}$ at both the ER conditions. Interestingly, the flame neck was found thinner at ER, $\Phi = 0.43$ and a slightly bent flame towards at right side was observed.

3.3. CO, CO₂ and NO_x emissions

3.3.1. Emissions at varying ER and TL

Experimental flue gas data were analyzed using regression modelling and the results were analysed to check the emission responses across a

Fig. 18. Quadratic response of flue gas emissions O₂, CO, CO₂ and NO_x at varying ER conditions and at individual thermal loads (10–25 kW).

Fig. 19. Pre-processing of flame image samples; (a). Edge detection (b). Binary image (c). Pre-processed image.

wide range of combustion conditions, especially for $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$ and $10 \text{ kW} \leq \text{TL} \leq 25 \text{ kW}$ (see Fig. 17). As expected, O₂ concentrations were inversely correlated with Φ , while , CO, CO₂ and NO_x

pollutants emissions showed a direct correlation in the examined range. In particular, pollutant emissions were the lowest under very lean mixture conditions and increased as stoichiometry conditions were approached.

More specifically, the highest CO concentration (550 ppm) was noticed at $\Phi = 0.70$, while the lowest (53 ppm) recorded at $\Phi = 0.50$. It is important to mention that these CO concentration are partly produced from fuel bound CO fractions present in the PG flow. Following the same trend, NO_x emissions peaked at 275 ppm at $\Phi = 0.70$, and were lowest (55 ppm) at $\Phi = 0.45$. In case of CO₂, emissions ranged from 10–15 % across the range $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$.

At fixed ER Φ , an increasing trend in NO_x emissions was detected with rising TL conditions, indicating a direct dependency on the TLs and an indirect influence of N₂ present in the PG flow. These NO_x emissions

Fig. 20. Post-processing of flame images; (a). Pre-processed FLIR image (b). Grey scale flame image (c). Final flame image.

were identified as fuel- NO_x emissions which arise from nitrogen compounds bound in the fuel rather than from thermal NO_x formation due to the relatively low combustion temperature and, therefore, thermal NO_x formation. This is supported by the observation that NO_x levels did not significantly vary at Φ values of 0.45, 0.55, and 0.65 when flame temperatures remained below 1000 °C. However, NO_x emissions increased notably as TLs rose from 10 kW to 25 kW under fixed lean conditions. Hence, this increase is more accurately attributed to the presence of fuel-bound nitrogen. Moreover, CO_2 emissions were found to be more sensitive to changes in Φ than to TL, while CO emissions were influenced solely by the Φ , not by TL.

To further elucidate key correlations, line charts of emissions data were extracted using quadratic regression analysis, as shown in Fig. 18. This approach enabled a clearer visualization of emission trends across changing ERs at fixed TLs ranging from 10 kW to 25 kW. Consistent with previous observations, O_2 concentrations showed inverse correlation with Φ , while CO, CO_2 and NO_x emissions increased with higher Φ in the range of $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$. In particular, the emission trends of O_2 , CO, and CO_2 emissions were relatively consistent from 10 kW to 25 kW, however, NO_x emissions appeared slightly different. For instance, NO_x emissions (see the secondary vertical axis of line charts of Fig. 18), notably remained relatively stable between 10 kW and 20 kW but rose sharply from approximately 200 ppm to 300 ppm between 20 kW and 25 kW. This non-linear increase at higher thermal loads in this graph suggests further evidence of prominent fuel-prompt NO_x formation. This behavior highlights NO_x emissions as a particularly complex and important subject for further investigation in future work.

4. Conclusions

In this work, green PG with a stable composition, 1.90 % CH_4 , 18.50 % H_2 , 8.85 % CO_2 , 22.20 % CO, 7.40 % H_2O , and 41.15 % N_2 , was experimentally obtained from gasification of wood packaging waste (disused pellets). This PG was combusted in a custom-designed flexible combustion test-rig to investigate fundamental flame parameters and flue gas emissions.

The employment of IR thermal imaging technique on confined PG flame presented effective visualizations of the flame temperature field and flame shape at various ER (Φ) across the range of Φ ($0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$) and TL ($10 \text{ kW} \leq \text{TL} \leq 25 \text{ kW}$).

In particular, the time-resolved thermal images of PG flame revealed the spatial-temporal evolution of flame temperature fields and flame shapes under different lean ER conditions. To process the flame data, a pixel-based correlation technique was developed enabling the

construction of non-intrusive flame temperature field from IR images. These temperature fields were found to be highly sensitive to changes in ER or fuel-air mixture strength.

The stable and efficient PG combustion process occurred at TL ~ 24 kW and near stoichiometric ER ($\Phi = 0.85$); however, under the lean ER of 0.43, the flame temperature dropped, leading to PG flame destabilization and reduced combustion efficiency. Time-averaged thermal images showed the full flame spread within the combustion chamber enabling a comprehensive evaluation of flame behavior.

At low-to-medium TL (~ 10 kW), re-stabilization of the PG flame was observed even under ultra-lean conditions when a minor fraction ($\sim 4\text{--}5\%$) of backup methane was added. The MPG1 mixture at low TLs was initially unstable, but methane addition effectively restored flame stability.

Across all ER conditions, the hottest region of the flame consistently occurred along the vertical y-axis of the combustion chamber between 130 mm and 212 mm from the burner outlet. Both intrusive and non-intrusive measurements confirmed the presence of low temperature gradients within the chamber, indicating efficient and uniform combustion of PG.

In parallel, the combined effects of ER and TL on flue gas emissions (O_2 , CO, CO_2 , and NO_x) were analyzed. As expected, O_2 concentrations decreased with increasing Φ , while CO, CO_2 , and NO_x emissions showed direct correlations with Φ across the range $0.45 \leq \Phi \leq 0.70$. At very lean ER ($\Phi = 0.45$), minimal emissions were observed: 35 ppm CO, 10 % CO_2 , and 55 ppm NO_x ; in contrast, maximum emissions were recorded at $\Phi = 0.70$ and TL ≈ 10 kW, with 530 ppm CO, 14 % CO_2 , and 155 ppm NO_x .

Regression analysis further revealed that NO_x emissions were strongly influenced by TL at fixed ER values. Specifically, when TL increased from 20 kW to 25 kW, NO_x emissions rose markedly from 200 ppm to 300 ppm. This trend supports the hypothesis of fuel- NO_x as the dominant formation mechanism under these conditions, with emissions primarily driven by nitrogen compounds bound in the fuel rather than by thermal NO_x pathways.

The contribution of fuel-bound nitrogen (N_2) to NO_x formation can be reduced by enhancing the mixing efficiency of the fuel-air mixture prior to combustion. This can be achieved in future studies through improved burner design, the incorporation of swirl-induced mixing, and the application of air-staging techniques.

5. Novelty and research significance

This experimental work investigates the combustion feasibility and flame stability of PG derived from the gasification of wood packaging

waste. A novel IR thermal imaging technique was implemented to explore the flame temperature distribution and monitor flue gas emissions from turbulent PG flames confined within the combustion chamber. Examining the combustion stability of alternative green fuels under ultra-lean turbulent flame conditions is crucial for advancing clean combustion research. Understanding the interaction between turbulent flows and PG flames can inform effective flame control strategies for industrial burners. This research represents a significant contribution to the advancement of clean combustion technology promoting sustainable heat solutions for high-temperature industrial processes that are challenging to decarbonize.

Appendix A.: Flame image processing

Image pre-processing

Preprocessing methodologies for flame images are presented in better details in this Annex: flame zone and its boundaries are retrieved with the application of an edge detection algorithm. These edge detection methods are an important step in developing advanced flame monitoring techniques for flames in combustion systems [27]. Following these methods, flame images were exported from the thermal camera software in the form of csv file with radiometric RGB scale and pre-processed through specific tools and Python codes using different library packages. This is done for image filtering and clear visualization of flame zone. To this aim, these images were extracted within time windows of required operating points. The step-by-step procedure is given as follows;

1. Both the FLIR flame images (with and without thermocouples) were extracted from thermal camera recordings in RGB format at selected flame conditions. The image resolution window of size 344×357 pixels were chosen as area of interest for flame image analysis. The size and shape of images were kept consistent during the pre-processing operation. For example, as shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20, an instantaneous frame image from the thermal camera recording was chosen as a sample image to explain the flame image processing procedure of a FLIR image at ER, $\Phi = 0.85$.
2. The flame image was pre-processed to eliminate the background noise and enhance the most intense flame region, making them more prominent against the background with well-defined boundaries, using a Gaussian filter operation.
3. To isolate the intense foreground flame from the background, the Sobel operator was applied to detect the flame edges (high gradient intensities in the y and z directions) or boundary around the flame as shown in Fig. 19 (a). Flame edges refer to a collection of discontinuous points of an image representing the drastic change in grayscale value in the y and z directions as well as the angular direction $a(y,z)$. The flame edges were identified by taking the higher-order derivatives or gradients of the function $f(y,z)$ in the 2D image.

Where g_y and g_z are vectors in the y and z directions. Normally, the higher-order derivatives give more efficient edge detection.

4. A mask was generated by converting these images into a binary field. In this mask, the region enclosed by the flame boundary corresponds to the white region, while the remaining (outer) region corresponds to the black one, as depicted in Fig. 19 (b). Subsequently, the pixel data of the white region in the binary image were substituted with thermal data from the FLIR image, as illustrated in Fig. 19 (c). These pre-processed images with clear boundaries of the isolated intense flame zone were processed further in post-processing steps to obtain the corrected flame temperature field.

A.2. Post-processing and sample result

The post-processing methodology for the correction of flame images is as follows.

1. As a first step in post-processing, the range of thermal data was acquired by determining the range (maximum and minimum pixel magnitudes) of pre-processed, RGB flame image
2. The pre-processed RGB images was converted into greyscale to find the greyscale range of image as shown in Fig. 20 (b). Importantly, consistency in terms of image shape and size was ensured in all the flame images during the post-processing steps.
3. The grey scale level of the sample is a 16 bit image ranging from 0 to 255. Using these grey and RGB scale ranges, a mapping function was created to determine the greyscale and thermal data at each pixel of the image

$$\text{Greyscale} = \left(\frac{\text{RGBscale} - \text{MinTemperature}}{\text{TemperatureRange}} \right) \times \text{Greyscalerange} + \text{MinGreyscale}$$

4. Grey scale value were converted into thermal data by mapping function while keeping the image size consistent

$$\text{Temperature} = \left(\frac{\text{Greyscale} - \text{MinGreyscale}}{\text{Greyscalerange}} \right) \times \text{TemperatureRange} + \text{MinTemperature}$$

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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5. The reference location was defined in the yz-plane according to the reference thermocouple coordinate (y, z) in the flame image (comprising thermocouples). The pixel-based correlation factor was defined at the reference location using the grey scale and temperature value, this factor is the ratio of thermocouple temperature and greyscale value

$$\text{Correlation factor} = \frac{\text{Thermocouple temperature}}{\text{Greyscale}}$$

Based on the correlation factor, the thermal data of the flame image (without TC) was modified by rescaling the thermal data to achieve the corrected flame temperature field as shown in Fig. 20

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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